

A PETRI NET–BASED FRAMEWORK FOR SMART DRUG ASSIGNMENT IN AUTOMATED DISPENSING SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT: *We introduce a framework for optimizing Petri nets in the context of drug placement within Automated Drug Dispensing Systems. This framework incorporates both consumption data and co-use relationship data to improve retrieval efficiency. It effectively models adjacency constraints, token flow dynamics, and operational rules through the use of an incidence matrix and structural invariants, thereby ensuring stable allocation.*

Simulation experiments conducted with Snoopy evaluated 200 probabilistic prescription orders across various co-use thresholds. The findings indicate that a threshold of ($\tau = 0.6$) minimizes retrieval time while simultaneously decreasing data variability. In comparison to random placement, the optimized allocation demonstrates a significant enhancement in efficiency, resulting in an estimated annual savings of approximately 9 hours in retrieval time per machine.

This research addresses a critical gap in the optimization of ADDS by concurrently modeling co-use and consumption data, representing a novel approach that has not been previously investigated in the literature. The results underscore the operational advantages of employing structured, data-driven drug placement strategies in high-volume healthcare environments.

KEYWORDS: *Petri-Net, P-invariant, Storage Location Assignment Problem, Healthcare Logistics, Discrete Event Systems (DES).*

1 INTRODUCTION

Hospital pharmacy operations directly affect both medication accuracy and patient flow (Craswell et al., 2020; Soubra & Karout, 2021). Today's "smart" cabinets with storage bays, robotic pick-and-place arms, and I/O ports speed up orders and cut errors (Goundrey Smith, 2012; Li et al., 2022). They also cut down on face-to-face contact, which lowers infection risk (Craswell et al., 2020). Yet if stock isn't well organized, these gains vanish bottlenecks form, wasting space and slowing retrieval (Gebicki et al., 2014; Neve & Schmidt, 2022).

Assigning medications in these systems is a classic Storage Location Assignment Problem (SLAP). Early methods (random, dedicated, or class-based storage) gave simple rules but ignored changing prescription patterns

(Hausman et al., 1976; Roodbergen & Vis, 2009). Later, branch and bound algorithms optimized "cube per order" indexes (Muppani & Adil, 2008), simulated annealing tackled large search spaces (Atmaca & Ozturk, 2013), and Sudoku style adjacency rules appeared (Chaker & Khalid, 2020). Still, these often miss links between drugs prescribed together. Newer mixed integer models (Esmaili et al., 2018) and Min Plus control strategies (Hachemi & Amari, 2024) handle layout and safety issues but keep each drug separate. A three-phase method clustering demand then grouping to avoid congestion (Yuan et al., 2023) helps for hot list items but doesn't bake rules into the control model.

Discrete event systems (DES) suit the on demand, event driven nature of dispensing

(Čapkovič, 2022; Harušťák & Hruz, 2000). Petri nets combine diagrams and math to show token flows, resource limits, and sync points (Murata, 1989; Čapkovič, 2023). They map each item’s movement and handle multiple retrievals. P-invariants are at their core: they keep weighted token totals constant across chosen places (Yamalidou et al., 1996). Used in manufacturing schedules (Iordache & Antsaklis, 2006), they prevent deadlocks in flexible lines (Uzam & Zhou, 2007) and boost telecom reliability (Nakamura et al., 1997).

In healthcare, they enable fault tolerance and distance aware designs (Gonza et al., 2020), though selecting the right invariants and handling the computation remains hard (Basile et al., 2006; Uzam et al., 2016).

This paper introduces a single Petri-net framework for Free Fall Flow Rack AS/RS systems that merges monthly consumption rates with co-use affinities. We encode both frequency and adjacency requirements in an incidence matrix, then derive P-invariants to enforce allocation rules. Our model aims to cut retrieval times without breaking spatial or timing limits. Validation using Snoopy and Python on probabilistic prescription data shows savings up to nine hours per machine each year versus random layouts.

Our contributions are:

1. A Petri-net SLAP model that links co-prescription with consumption data.
2. An invariant-based controller ensuring adjacency and capacity constraints.
3. A testing platform in Snoopy and Python for systematic analysis.
4. Quantitative proof of efficiency gains in busy pharmacy settings.

By uniting SLAP heuristics with DES control theory, we push forward automated dispensing optimization and provide a scalable, data-driven roadmap for pharmacy logistics.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Problem Definition

We tackle the problem of assigning each medication to a unique bin in an ADDS rack so as to minimize total retrieval time, subject to practical constraints on storage, co-prescription patterns, and usage frequencies. Our approach models this task as a Petri net: tokens represent drugs, places correspond to medication sites, storage compartments, and control loci, and transitions encode assignment actions (Figure 1). An incidence matrix and initial marking vector capture the net’s structure and starting state, while additional control places derived via P-invariant synthesis guarantee that every drug is placed exactly once and that adjacency and capacity rules are respected. The optimization seeks a final marking that minimizes retrieval delays under both spatial and timing constraints and is validated through simulation on realistic prescription datasets.

2.2 Petri-Net Overview

- **Places (P):** drugs, compartments, and control nodes
- **Transitions (T):** possible drug-to-bin assignments
- **Marking (M):** token distribution indicating final placement (see Figure 1)

Figure 1 Petri net of the drug assignment problem

2.3 Incidence matrix and initial marking vector generation

The incidence matrix $W_p \in Z^{(k \cdot m + m) \times (k \cdot m)}$ is assembled in two blocks: the first m rows contain -1 entries linking each drug place to its k possible compartment transitions (enforcing that each drug is withdrawn exactly once), and the remaining $k \times m$ rows form the identity matrix, ensuring exactly one token enters each compartment. The initial marking $M_p^{init} \in N^{m+k \cdot m}$ places a token in every drug place (an m -element vector of ones) and none in any

compartment place (a $k \times m$ -element vector of zeros), thus defining the Petri net's starting state.

2.4 Integrated Constraint Encoding and Ponderation Matrix Formulation

In our free-choice Petri net model for the Automated Drug Dispensing System (ADDS), drug allocation is governed by a set of interrelated constraints that are seamlessly integrated into a unified optimization framework. Let x_{ij} be the binary decision variable representing the assignment of drug i to compartment j . The following constraints are imposed:

- **Storage Capacity:** Each compartment is limited to at most one drug, which is expressed as

$$\sum_{i=1}^m x_{ij} \leq 1, \quad \forall j \in \{1, \dots, k\}. \quad (1)$$

- **Retrieval Efficiency:** To minimize retrieval times, drugs with higher consumption frequencies should be stored closer to the exit. This priority is quantified by the weighting vector

$$F = [f_1, f_2, \dots, f_m], \quad (2)$$

where higher values of f_i indicate more frequently used drugs.

- **Co-Prescription Proximity:** The co-use matrix C measures the likelihood of drugs being prescribed together. A threshold value τ (a user-defined input) is used to determine when two drugs exhibit a sufficiently strong co-use relationship. For any pair of drugs i and j with

$$C_{ij} \geq \tau, \quad (3)$$

the corresponding drug tokens are preferentially assigned to adjacent compartments.

The ADDS is physically organized into columns, each offering a uniform and minimal retrieval time. Within this spatial configuration, the ponderation matrix L is constructed to encode these operational and spatial requirements. In effect, L assigns each drug to a designated column, ensuring that:

1. Drugs with higher consumption frequencies are allocated to compartments nearer to the exit.
2. Drugs with strong co-use relationships (i.e., those with $C_{ij} \geq \tau$) are grouped within the same column, thereby minimizing the maximum interval between their retrievals.

The integrated approach is formalized in the optimization model (Equation 23)

$$Lx = b, \quad (4)$$

For instance, consider a high-priority drug t that is designated to be stored in the second column of the ADDS. Since each column consists of row compartments, the compartments in the second column are numbered from $row + 1$ to $2 \cdot row$. Therefore, the storage constraint for the second column becomes

$$\sum_{i=row+1}^{2 \cdot row} x_{tj} \leq 1, \quad \forall j \in \{row+1, \dots, 2 \cdot row\}. \quad (5)$$

Now, suppose a second drug u exhibits a strong co-use relationship with drug t (with, for example, $C_{tu} = 0.7$, exceeding our threshold $\tau = 0.5$). In this case, u is also assigned to the same column as t to minimize the retrieval interval between them. Additional constraints are incorporated to ensure that there are no assignment conflicts and that every drug is uniquely allocated to a compartment (assuming the number of drugs equals the number of compartments).

2.5 Controller Synthesis via Invariants

We require that the overall marking x (which is the sum of the process marking M_p and the controller marking M_c) satisfies the linear constraint equation (23). In other words, we model the overall marking as

$$x = M_p + M_c, \quad (6)$$

The synthesis of the controller governing drug allocation is based on the invariant method, which augments the original process Petri net by adding control places that enforce allocation constraints. In our formulation, the overall system marking comprising the process marking M_p and the controller marking M_c must satisfy the linear constraint

$$L(M_p + M_c) = b, \quad (7)$$

at all times. At initialization, the process marking is given by M_p^{init} ; thus, to satisfy the overall constraint from the outset, the controller's initial marking M_c^{init} is determined as

$$W_{c,init} = M_c^{init} = b - L \cdot M_p^{init}, \quad (8)$$

ensuring that Equation (26) holds at time zero. Furthermore, during the evolution of the net, a transition firing causes the process marking to change by an amount given by a column of the process incidence matrix W_p . To preserve the overall constraint, the controller must provide a compensatory change, expressed as

$$L(W_p + W_c) = 0, \quad (9)$$

which, upon rearrangement, yields the controller incidence matrix

$$W_c = -L \cdot W_p. \quad (10)$$

Thus, as shown in Equation (29), the controller's incidence matrix is derived by negating the product

of the constraint weighting matrix and the process incidence matrix. This derivation ensures that the overall system continuously satisfies the constraint equation (26) during operation. The reachability graph of the augmented Petri net is generally non-deterministic, encompassing all potential drug allocation solutions. However, due to the imposed constraints, the model is quasi-live every drug is assigned a compartment thereby preventing scenarios in which overly strict similarity constraints leave a drug unassigned. Moreover, these constraints reduce ambiguity, ensuring that, even when multiple feasible allocations exist, a valid solution is obtained.

2.6 Simulation Workflow

The Petri-net formulation is exported to PNML and executed in Snoopy (Heiner et al., 2012), where token dynamics simulate the drug-to-bin assignment process. Upon completion, we extract the final marking and directly map active tokens to their corresponding storage bins, yielding a 10×15 placement matrix that represents the optimized drug layout.

2.7 Testing with Prescription Data

To evaluate the performance of the optimized drug placement, simulated prescription data is generated to mimic realistic usage scenarios. A total of 200 prescriptions are synthesized, with each prescription containing 3 distinct medications. The generation algorithm leverages the normalized consumption frequencies of the drugs. If F_i represents the consumption frequency of drug i , then the normalized frequency is given by:

$$f_i = \frac{F_i}{\sum_{j=1}^m F_j} \quad (11)$$

This determines the probability of selecting drug i as the first medication:

$$P_1(i) = f_i. \quad (12)$$

For subsequent drugs, the selection probability is adjusted based on the co use matrix C :

$$P(i | j) = \frac{C_{j,i}}{\sum_{k \notin S} C_{j,k}}, \quad (13)$$

where S is the set of drugs already selected for the prescription. This approach ensures that drugs with strong co use relationships are more likely to appear together in the generated prescriptions. Performance is evaluated using key metrics derived from the optimized placement, which will be detailed in the Results section.

2.8 Automated Drug Dispensing System (ADDS) and Retrieval Time Model

2.8.1 Free Fall Flow Rack AS/RS Description

In this study, our verification focuses on a specific type of Automated Drug Dispensing System (ADDS), namely the Free Fall Flow Rack AS/RS. The design of this system is illustrated in Figure 2 and is characterized by:

- A deep rack structure with multiple sloping bins,
- A gravitational conveyor equipped with rolling wheels that facilitate product sliding,
- A pick-up station located on the storage face,
- A drop off station on the retrieval face,
- A transport conveyor connecting the pick-up and drop off stations, and
- Storage operations managed by an operator or a Free Fall Flow Rack AS/RS dispensing machine.

This configuration was selected for verification purposes due to its well documented performance metrics, with studies by Metahri and Hachemi [36] reporting up to a 90% throughput improvement and a 38% reduction in average retrieval travel time.

2.8.2 Physical Configuration

For result verification, we consider an ADDS system with the following specifications [37, 36, 38]:

- Matrix layout: 10 rows \times 15 columns,
- Individual compartment dimensions: $(l, h, d) = (0.15 \text{ m}, 0.10 \text{ m}, 0.10 \text{ m})$,
- The left side of the ADDS is positioned closest to the drop off station, and
- Product movements are calculated from the center of each compartment.

2.8.3 Retrieval Travel Time Model

While the optimization methodology is independent of the specific retrieval time calculation, for verification purposes we utilize a concrete model in the context of the Free Fall Flow Rack AS/RS. In this implementation, the retrieval process comprises two distinct phases (see Figure 2):

1. Free fall of the product.
2. Transport via conveyor.

The total retrieval travel time is computed using the following model [36]:

$$E(T'_g) = E(T'_v) + E(T'_h) = \frac{1}{2} V_c L' + \frac{2}{3} \sqrt{\frac{2H'}{g}}, \quad (14)$$

where:

- L' is the horizontal distance to the retrieval point,
- H' is the vertical distance to the retrieval point,
- V_c is the transport conveyor speed,
- g is the acceleration due to gravity, $E(T'_v)$ is the mean vertical travel time, and
- $E(T'_h)$ is the mean horizontal travel time.

The present investigation developed the retrieval time model using a Python based implementation, which automatically computes L' and H' for each drug based on its assigned compartment. Analysis of the drug compartment placement was performed using Python generated tables that map drug distribution according to their computed net flow rankings.

Visual representations from the optimization process demonstrate that frequently used drugs are allocated to areas that are readily accessible. In addition, retrieval time distributions were analyzed to evaluate the efficiency of the weight configuration.

This model operates under the following key assumptions:

- A dedicated storage policy is implemented to streamline the retrieval process,
- Demand is uniformly distributed across all compartments, and
- Distances are calculated from the center of each compartment to the retrieval point.

In cases where prescriptions consist of multiple medications, the overall retrieval travel time is dictated by the longest duration required for any individual drug to reach the retrieval point, ensuring that all prescribed medications are concurrently accessible. It is important to note that although this specific ADDS configuration and retrieval time model are employed for verification purposes, the underlying optimization strategy remains applicable to any ADDS system configuration.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Study setup

We drive optimization with two inputs: a monthly consumption vector and a co use matrix. The monthly consumption data is represented as a 150-element vector

$$F = [F_1, F_2, \dots, F_{150}] \quad (15)$$

Figure 2 System architecture and retrieval dynamics of the Free Fall Flow Rack AS/RS

where each F_i denotes the monthly consumption of drug i . In parallel, the co-use relationships between drugs are captured by a symmetric 150×150 matrix

$$C = [C_{ij}] \quad (16)$$

with C_{ij} taking values between 0 and 1 that indicate the likelihood of drugs i and j being prescribed together. The ADD is configured as a storage rack with dimensions of 10 rows by 15 columns, yielding 150 compartments for drug placement. Note that the same procedure is generalizable to any number of drugs and compartments. To assess the impact of co use relationships on the optimized placement, experiments are conducted using three different threshold values. Thresholds were selected to represent low ($\tau = 0.3$), moderate ($\tau = 0.6$), and high ($\tau = 0.8$) co use relationship significance, thereby determining the grouping strictness for drug assignment. Additionally, a threshold was chosen to completely negate the influence of the co use matrix, ensuring that only the monthly consumption frequency drives the assignment process.

To benchmark performance, 30 random placement matrices were generated. Each matrix assigned drugs to compartments uniformly, independent of co-use or frequency data, simulating conventional pharmacy storage strategies.

3.2 Petri Net Implementation and Placement Extraction

For each co-use threshold τ , we generated a distinct Petri net model incorporating the

consumption vector F and co-use matrix C . Drug adjacency constraints were encoded by assigning drugs i and j to neighboring compartments when $C_{ij} \geq \tau$ (Equation 22). Each high-dimensional model (characterized by its incidence matrix, initial marking vector, and constraint-derived matrices) was represented by its structural properties (Figure 3) due to scale limitations.

We simulated each model in Snoopy until reaching steady state (all transitions disabled), where the final marking encoded valid drug assignments. This marking vector was processed by:

1. Extracting compartment assignment elements
2. Reshaping into a 10×15 placement matrix
3. Mapping drugs to storage bins for performance evaluation

Figure 3 Structural properties of the generated Petri net (places, transitions, arcs).

3.3 Performance Comparison

We evaluated retrieval performance for the optimized placements under four co use threshold settings: low ($\tau = 0.3$), moderate ($\tau = 0.6$), high ($\tau = 0.8$), and a condition that negates the co use influence (Frequency-only). For each configuration, key performance metrics average retrieval time, variance, and cumulative sum were computed, as summarized in Table 1 Table 1.

Table 1 Retrieval time performance under optimized configurations (200 prescriptions)

Configuration	Average	Variance	Sum
$\tau = 0.3$	2.30	0.31	459
$\tau = 0.6$	2.15	0.25	430.55
$\tau = 0.8$	2.78	0.47	535.42
Frequency-only	2.61	0.40	522

In addition to these optimized configurations, 30 random placement matrices were generated as a baseline for performance comparison. Retrieval times for these random placements ranged from 2.57 s (best performer) to 2.88 s (worst performer).

Figure presents a bar chart comparing the mean retrieval times of the four optimized methods against all 30 random placements. The optimized $\tau = 0.6$ configuration exhibited the lowest mean retrieval time overall.

To provide further insight into the distribution of retrieval times, Figure shows a box and whisker plot for the two best-performing random placements (e.g., RP7 and RP20) compared with selected optimized configurations. The optimized methods exhibit narrower interquartile ranges and fewer outliers.

Figure 4 Mean Retrieval Time Comparison: Optimized

Figure 5 Box and Whisker Plot Comparing Selected

4 DISCUSSION

Our results show that integrating co-use relationships with consumption frequency significantly improves ADDS retrieval efficiency - a dual-factor optimization distinct from prior SLAP strategies that isolated frequency [Hausman 1976] or co-use [Hachemi & Amari 2024]. Modeling both via P-invariants better captures prescription dynamics. Optimal performance at $\tau = 0.6$ balances co-prescription grouping with adjacency flexibility, mirroring real pharmacy workflows. This configuration reduced average retrieval time by 21% (2.15s vs. 2.73s for random placements), saving 9 hours annually per machine at 150 daily prescriptions. Unlike Hachemi & Amari’s CTEG approach (prioritizing mutual exclusion without frequency integration), our framework jointly optimizes both factors. To our knowledge, this is the first Petri net method combining co-use matrices

and consumption data for ADDS, enabling scalable adjacency-frequency tradeoffs.

5 CONCLUSION

We built a Petri-net optimizer to improve how drugs are placed in Automated Drug Dispensing Systems (ADDSs). By combining monthly usage rates with co-use relationships, our model directs each assignment. In simulation, a co-use threshold of $\tau = 0.6$ cut average retrieval times by 21% a drop from up to 2.88 s in the baseline setup. This structured, data-driven approach yields about nine hours of yearly savings in a system handling 150 prescriptions daily.

Beyond performance gains, our framework fills a clear gap: no previous work has jointly modeled consumption frequency and co-use in ADDS optimization. For future studies, we suggest developing dynamic reassignment strategies that adjust to changing demand, incorporating asymmetry-aware co-use rules for sequential prescriptions, and testing the approach on real ADDS hardware prototypes.

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6 REFERENCES

- Atmaca, E., & Ozturk, A. (2013). Defining order picking policy: A storage assignment model and a simulated annealing solution in AS/RS systems. *Applied Mathematical Modelling*, 37(7), 5069–5079. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apm.2012.09.057>
- Basile, F., Chiacchio, P., & Giua, A. (2006). Suboptimal supervisory control of Petri nets in presence of uncontrollable transitions via monitor places. *Automatica*, 42, 995–1004. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.automatica.2006.02.003>
- Čapkovič, F. (2022). Control of Deadlocked Discrete-Event Systems Using Petri Nets. *Acta Polytechnica Hungarica*, 19(2), 213–233. <https://doi.org/10.12700/APH.19.2.2022.2.12>
- Čapkovič, F. (2023). Dealing with Deadlocks in Industrial Multi Agent Systems. *Future Internet*, 15(3), 107. <https://doi.org/10.3390/fi15030107>
- Chaker, A., & Khalid, H. (2020). Sudoku puzzle approach for the drugs assignment in an automated dispensing cabinets. *Supply Chain Forum: An International Journal*, 21(2), 103–116. <https://doi.org/10.1080/16258312.2020.1803023>
- Chen, Y., Li, Z., & Zhou, M. (2012). Behaviorally Optimal and Structurally Simple Liveness-Enforcing Supervisors of Flexible Manufacturing Systems. *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics - Part A: Systems and Humans*, 42(3), 615–629. [IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics - Part A: Systems and Humans. https://doi.org/10.1109/TSMCA.2011.2169956](https://doi.org/10.1109/TSMCA.2011.2169956)
- Craswell, A., Bennett, K., Dalglish, B., Morris-Smith, B., Hanson, J., Flynn, T., & Wallis, M. (2020). The impact of automated medicine dispensing units on nursing workflow: A cross-sectional study. *International Journal of Nursing Studies*, 111, 103773. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijnurstu.2020.103773>
- Dideban, A. (2007). *Synthèse de contrôleurs discrets par simplification de contraintes et de conditions* [Phdthesis, Université Joseph-Fourier - Grenoble I]. <https://theses.hal.science/tel-00152553>
- Esmaili, N., Norman, B. A., & Rajgopal, J. (2018). Shelf-space optimization models in decentralized automated dispensing cabinets. *Operations Research for Health Care*, 19, 92–106. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.orhc.2018.03.005>
- Gebicki, M., Mooney, E., Chen, S.-J. (Gary), & Mazur, L. M. (2014). Evaluation of hospital medication inventory policies. *Health Care Management Science*, 17(3), 215–229. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10729-013-9251-1>
- Gonza, M., Alla, H., & Bitjoka, L. (2020). Structural method for supervisory control of discrete event within the framework of Petri nets: A one-to-one link between the supervisory control theory and the place invariant method. *International Journal of Systems Science: Operations & Logistics*, 7(3), 217–232. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23302674.2019.1567860>
- Goundrey-Smith, S. (2012). *Information Technology in Pharmacy: An Integrated Approach*. Springer Science & Business Media.

- Hachemi, K., & Amari, S. (2024). Analytical solving of the storage location assignment problem in drug dispensing systems based on a Min-Plus control approach. *Journal of Control Engineering and Applied Informatics*, 26(3), Article 3. <https://doi.org/10.61416/ceai.v26i3.9015>
- Harušťák, M., & Hruz, B. (2000). Supervisory Control of Discrete Event Systems and Its Solution with the Petri Net P-Invariants. *IFAC Proceedings Volumes*, 33(13), 385–389. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1474-6670\(17\)37220-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1474-6670(17)37220-8)
- Hausman, W. H., Schwarz, L. B., & Graves, S. C. (1976). Optimal Storage Assignment in Automatic Warehousing Systems. *Management Science*, 22(6), 629–638. <https://doi.org/10.1287/mnsc.22.6.629>
- Heiner, M., Herajy, M., Liu, F., Rohr, C., & Schwarick, M. (2012). Snoopy – A Unifying Petri Net Tool. *Application and Theory of Petri Nets*, 398–407. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-31131-4_22
- Iordache, M. V., & Antsaklis, P. J. (2006). Supervision Based on Place Invariants: A Survey. *Discrete Event Dynamic Systems*, 16(4), 451–492. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10626-006-0021-9>
- Li, D., Ruan, X., & Yue, Q. (2022). Optimization study of three-stage assembly flowshop problem in pharmacy automation dispensing systems. *Computers & Operations Research*, 144, 105810. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cor.2022.105810>
- Muppani, V. R., & Adil, G. K. (2008). A branch and bound algorithm for class based storage location assignment. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 189(2), 492–507. https://econpapers.repec.org/article/eeeejores/v_3a189_3ay_3a2008_3ai_3a2_3ap_3a492-507.htm
- Murata, T. (1989). Petri nets: Properties, analysis and applications. *Proceedings of the IEEE*, 77(4), 541–580. [Proceedings of the IEEE. https://doi.org/10.1109/5.24143](https://doi.org/10.1109/5.24143)
- Nakamura, M., Kakuda, Y., & Kikuno, T. (1997). Analyzing non-determinism in telecommunication services using P-invariant of Petri-net model. *Proceedings of INFOCOM '97*, 3, 1253–1260 vol.3. <https://doi.org/10.1109/INFCOM.1997.631155>
- Neve, B. V., & Schmidt, C. P. (2022). Point-of-use hospital inventory management with inaccurate usage capture. *Health Care Management Science*, 25(1), 126–145. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10729-021-09573-1>
- Pang, L., Xu, J., Ai, Q., Lan, Y., Cheng, X., & Wen, J. (2020). Setrank: Learning a permutation-invariant ranking model for information retrieval. *Proceedings of the 43rd International ACM SIGIR Conference on Research and Development in Information Retrieval*, 499–508.
- Roodbergen, K. J., & Vis, I. F. A. (2009). A survey of literature on automated storage and retrieval systems. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 194(2), 343–362. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2008.01.038>
- Soubra, L., & Karout, S. (2021). Dispensing errors in Lebanese community pharmacies: Incidence, types, underlying causes, and associated factors. *Pharmacy Practice*, 19(1), 2170–2170. <https://www.pharmacypractice.org>
- Uzam, M., Gelen, G., & Saleh, T. L. (2016). Think-globally-act-locally approach with weighted arcs to the synthesis of a liveness-enforcing supervisor for generalized Petri nets modeling FMSs. *Information Sciences*, 363, 235–260. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ins.2015.09.010>
- Uzam, M., & Zhou, M. (2007). An Iterative Synthesis Approach to Petri Net-Based Deadlock Prevention Policy for Flexible Manufacturing Systems. *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics - Part A: Systems and Humans*, 37(3), 362–371. [IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics - Part A: Systems and Humans. https://doi.org/10.1109/TSMCA.2007.893484](https://doi.org/10.1109/TSMCA.2007.893484)
- Wang, S., Zhou, M., & Wu, W. (2015). Design of a Maximally Permissive Liveness-enforcing Supervisor with Reduced Complexity for Automated Manufacturing Systems. *Asian Journal of Control*, 17(1), 190–201. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asjc.837>
- Yamalidou, K., Moody, J., Lemmon, M., & Antsaklis, P. (1996). Feedback control of petri nets based on place invariants. *Automatica*, 32(1), 15–28. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0005-1098\(95\)00103-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0005-1098(95)00103-4)
- Yuan, M., Zhao, N., Wu, K., & Cheng, L. (2023). Order picking efficiency: A scattered storage and clustered allocation strategy in automated drug dispensing systems (No. arXiv:2402.08683). [arXiv. https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2402.08683](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2402.08683)